

GRAPHENE BASED POLY(VINYL ALCOHOL) NANOCOMPOSITES: EFFECT OF HUMIDITY CONTENT

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1 Introduction

Graphene and graphene oxide (GO) are widely studied in several fields of materials science and engineering. In particular, recent progress has shown that graphene-based materials may have a deep impact on the development of electronic and optoelectronic devices, chemical sensors, materials for energy storage and nanocomposites [1]. In recent years, a variety of processing routes have been reported for dispersing both graphene and GO-derived fillers [2] into polymer matrices. In particular, solution- and melt-mixing, in-situ polymerization, emulsion polymerization, lyophilization methods and phase transfer techniques have been the most widely investigated. Moreover, several types of polymers have been investigated as possible matrices for graphene and GO based nanocomposites, including both thermoplastic and thermosetting matrices [2-4].

Due to its solubility in polar solvents including water, poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVOH) has been one of the most intensively studied matrices for the preparation of graphene and GO-based nanocomposites by solution dispersion [5, 6]. The thermal stability of PVOH up to relatively high temperatures has been also recently exploited for the application of mild thermal treatments on PVOH/GO nanocomposites in order to promote a thermal reduction of GO [7]. The occurrence of an in-situ reduction of graphene oxide has been confirmed by electrical resistivity measurements. In this manuscript, PVOH nanocomposites filled various amounts of both GO and chemically reduced graphene oxide (RGO) has been prepared. In particular the effect of the humidity content on the thermomechanical behaviour has been analyzed.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials and sample preparation

Fully hydrolyzed PVOH Celvol 350 (molecular weight = 100 kDa) was kindly supplied by Celanese (Dallas, USA). Graphite powder (particle size 20 microns) and hydrazine hydrate solution (yield = 50–60 %) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All reagents were analytical grade and used without any further purification.

GO was obtained from graphite according to the modified Hummers method [8]. GO powder was dispersed in distilled water by using high power sonication treatment. The obtained dispersion was centrifuged at 4,000 rpm for 1 h in order to remove non-exfoliated GO. Brownish homogenous suspensions of GO with concentration up to 10 mg/mL were obtained. Chemically (by using hydrazine) reduced GO (RGO) was prepared according to the literature indications [9]. In particular, hydrazine hydrate solution was added to aqueous PVOH-GO solution with a GO/hydrazine weight ratio of 1. The mixture was kept at 95 °C for 24 h under magnetic stirring. GO and RGO colloidal dispersions were added to aqueous solutions of PVOH (50 mg/mL) for nanocomposite preparation. The mixtures were sonicated for 1 min and then poured into an open silicon mould to allow the evaporation of the solvent. The obtained films had a thickness of about 25 microns. Nanocomposites with a filler content up to 9.4 wt% were produced.

Both dry and conditioned samples were analyzed. In particular dry samples were treated for 15 hours at 60 °C and stored under vacuum, while conditioned samples were prepared by exposing dry samples at a relative humidity of 50% at 23 °C for 2 weeks.

2.2 Measurements

Nanocomposites were fractured in liquid nitrogen, mounted on aluminium stub using a conductive adhesive without any further metallization and analyzed with a Zeiss Supra 40 field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM).

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements were performed with a Mettler DSC 30 calorimeter. A first heating ramp from 0 up to 240 °C was followed by a cooling stage from 240 to 0 °C and by a second heating ramp up to 240 °C. Both the heating and cooling rates were fixed at 10 °C/min, and all tests were conducted in nitrogen flushing at 100 mL/min.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) measurements were performed with a Mettler TG50 thermobalance at a heating rate of 10 °C/min from 40 to 600 °C under nitrogen flow (200 mL/min).

Uniaxial tensile tests at 23 °C and 50% relative humidity were performed with an Instron model 4502 tensile testing machine equipped with a 100 N load cell. Rectangular specimens with a length of 50 mm, a width of 5 mm and a thickness of about 25 microns were tested at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min. According to ISO 527 standard, an elastic modulus was evaluated as secant value between deformation levels of 0.05% and 0.25%. For each sample, at least five specimens were tested.

3 Results and Discussion

As shown in Figure 1, the adopted Hummers procedure yields GO in form of highly exfoliated lamellae.

FESEM micrographs of the cryofractured surface of nanocomposites evidence a highly homogenous dispersion of GO lamellae in the polymer matrix. After chemical reduction the initial amounts of 1 wt% and 9.4 wt% of GO are reduced to 0.4 wt% and 4.1 wt%, respectively. It is interesting to note how the RGO layers appear to be more homogeneously dispersed in the PVOH matrix. The analysis of the FESEM pictures of composites with a low amount of filler allowed us to estimate the specific surface area (SSA) values. For GO and RGO particles SSA values of about 1730 m²/g and 1020 m²/g, were respectively obtained. The estimated SSA value of GO is in good agreement with the scientific literature indications [10], while the SSA estimated

for RGO is significantly lower than the theoretical value of about 2600 m²/g reported for this material [4]. This means that RGO is probably aggregated in units of two or three layers.

The equilibrium moisture content of the samples conditioned at 23 °C and 50 % R.H. is reported in Figure 3 as a function of the weight content of GO and RGO. It can be noticed that the amount of moisture absorbed by the PVOH matrix is reduced as the filler content increases and that this reduction is higher for RGO- over GO-based nanocomposites.

The glass transition temperature (T_g) of the nanocomposites assessed by DSC measurements is reported in Figure 4. As expected, the T_g values of dried PVOH (77 °C) is markedly higher than that measured on conditioned PVOH (46 °C). Moreover, it is interesting to observe that T_g values slightly increase with the filler content, especially on dry specimens and for an elevated content of RGO particles.

As represented in Figure 5, TGA analysis evidenced a remarkable effect of the degradation temperature of the PVOH-based nanocomposites. In particular, both the onset and the peak degradation temperatures markedly increase as the nanofillers content increases. This effect is more pronounced for the nanocomposites containing RGO nanoparticles in comparison with those containing GO nanoparticles.

The tensile stress-strain curves of the investigated materials are reported in Figure 6 for both dry and conditioned samples. As expected, the mechanical behaviour of the dried and conditioned PVOH matrix is markedly different. In fact, the plasticizing effect of the absorbed water causes a decrease of the maximum stress and a concurrent increase of the deformation at break. The addition of nanofillers (both GO and RGO) causes a remarkable reduction of the deformation at break for both dry and conditioned samples, which is quantified in Figure 7. It can be noticed that, for a given filler amount, RGO nanoparticles are more effective than GO nanoparticles in reducing the deformation at break of both dry and conditioned PVOH matrix. This effect is surely due to the higher specific surface area and rigidity of RGO over GO nanoparticles and,

consequently, to the better efficacy in reducing the macromolecules mobility. By looking at the stress-strain curves reported in Figure 6, it clearly emerges that the investigated nanofillers (GO and RGO) are capable of strong modifications the stress at break values of PVOH matrix. In particular,

The effect of GO and RGO on the tensile strength of PVOH nanocomposites is highlighted in Figure 8 for dry and conditioned samples. It is worthwhile to note that both reinforcing and weakening effects can be observed, depending on the state of the PVOH matrix. In particular, for dry PVOH matrix a reduction of the tensile strength is reported while for the conditioned PVOH matrix a remarkable increase is observed. Moreover, the reinforcing (or weakening) effects are more pronounced when RGO particles are used.

Finally, for as the elastic modulus of the investigated composites is concerned, a beneficial effect can be observed when nanoparticles are added to PVOH both in the dry and conditioned states. Also for this property, a remarkable increase is observed especially when conditioned composites are considered and when RGO nanoparticles are added.

4 Conclusions

Both GO and RGO nanoparticles resulted to effectively improve the thermal degradation resistance of PVOH matrix. The mechanical properties were also remarkably affected by the insertion of nanoparticles in both dried and conditioned PVOH nanocomposites. Depending on the humidity content of the PVOH matrix, differences have been detected on the mechanical response. In particular, for dry PVOH matrix a reduction of the tensile strength is reported while for the conditioned PVOH matrix a remarkable increase is observed with the addition of both GO and RGO nanoparticles.

Fig. 1. FESEM micrographs of neat GO layers.

PVOH-GO 1.0 wt.-%

PVOH-RGO 0.4 wt.-%

PVOH-GO 9.4 wt.-%

PVOH-RGO 4.1 wt.-%

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of cryo-fracture surfaces of nanocomposites.

Fig. 3. Moisture content for PVOH-GO (▲) and PVOH-RGO (●) composites after conditioning at 23°C and 50%RH.

Fig. 4. Tg values of PVOH-GO (dry ▲, conditioned △) and PVOH-RGO (dry ●, conditioned ○).

Fig. 5. Onset degradation temperature (○, △) and degradation peak temperature (●, ▲) as a function of the filler content for PVOH-GO (▲, △) and PVOH-RGO (●, ○).

Fig. 6. stress-strain curves for PVOH-GO and PVOH-RGO composites dried and conditioned.

Fig. 7. Tensile strain at break (ϵ_{MAX}) for PVOH-GO (▲, △) and PVOH-RGO composites (●, ○) dried (○, △) and conditioned (●, ▲).

Fig. 8. Tensile strength (σ_{MAX}) for PVOH-GO (▲, △) and PVOH-RGO composites (●, ○) dried (○, △) and conditioned (●, ▲).

Fig. 9. Elastic modulus (E) for PVOH-GO (▲, △) and PVOH-RGO composites (●, ○) dried (○, △) and conditioned (●, ▲).

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